

ANATOMY OF LIGHT

Op. 1 (2025)

Op.1 ANATOMY OF LIGHT (2025) ca. 4'10"

Composed for the centennial concert series *Puccini nel 100° della morte* – Brescia, Novara & Riva del Garda.

Composition: Como/Brescia, 01–10 Apr 2024; rev. Feb and Jul–Aug 2025; final authorial text completed 05 Aug 2025

Form/structure: single-movement

Instrumentation: WOODWIND & PIANO DUET

Op. 1/a: ALTO SAXOPHONE (in Eb), PIANO | Op. 1/b: CLARINET (in Bb), PIANO

Note. Op. 1/a and Op. 1/b are alternative instrumentations for practical performance; both reflect the same textual state.

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PERFORMANCE NOTES

Accidentals

Accidentals apply **per measure** to all subsequent occurrences of the **same pitch**. Courtesy accidentals are used exclusively in cases where the natural (unaffected) note immediately follows the altered note.

Transposition

The score is notated in **sounding pitch** and is identical for both alternative instrumentations (Op.1/a–b). Both **parts** are in **transposed notation**.

Hand and Staff Assignments (piano part)

A. The **two staves** are assigned according to the player's hands, rather than functioning solely as a pitch grid:

- Upper staff = right hand
- Lower staff = left hand

This assignment governs the default reading of the score.

B. **Exceptions** (for crossings or shared registers) are frequent but always notated with:

1. **R.H.** (right hand) or **L.H.** (left hand) markings
2. **Cross-beaming**, which is used in this piece – alongside its rhythmic grouping function – to show the **movement of the hand** from one staff to the other; this applies strictly to the **beamed group**, not to subsequent notes unless otherwise marked.

Given the two-stave configuration, this **mixed notational approach** supports clearer reading in the **middle register** – preventing excessive ledger lines and clef changes.

Note. Lines are used to clarify **voice leading across staves**, not the motion of the hands.

Sustain pedal (piano part)

Pedal usage is left to the **performer's discretion**, based on harmonic considerations and usually on a per-measure basis. Pedal markings are not continuous and appear when a deviation from standard performance practice is intended.

PROGRAM NOTE

Anatomy of Light was composed as a tribute to Giacomo Puccini on the centenary of his death and premiered at the Bazzini Hall of the “L. Marenzio” Conservatory in Brescia, on 11 May 2024. This short, free-form work reflects on the relationship between musical legacy and the present, revisiting the style of early Puccini in an attempt to reconstruct the anatomy of a bygone aesthetic.

Though necessarily shaped by historical distance, this act of reconstruction yields a reward: it invites us to renew our engagement with Puccini's voice through a process of *presentification*. The piece reenacts the lyrical voice – not through a singer, but via instrumental means – echoing the spirit of 19th-century chamber arias. The use of the saxophone – an instrument largely foreign to Puccini's output – marks a deliberate departure from tradition. Yet it also gestures toward *Turandot*, where Puccini, in his late search for modern sounds and textures, included two alto saxophones. In this way, *Anatomy of Light* attempts to mirror the arc of Puccini's own evolution: the romantic impulse reaching toward modernism, underlying the fertile intergenerational dialogue that animates the most vital artistic traditions.

A brief yet pointed quote from *Un bel dì vedremo* concludes the piece, once again evoking that bygone era – and hinting, perhaps, at its return. The piece is also available in an alternative version for clarinet and piano.

ANATOMY OF LIGHT

(ALTO SAXOPHONE (in E \flat) or CLARINET (in B \flat) and PIANO)

Oneiric, sensuous ($\text{♩} = 63$)

ALEXANDRE CASACCIA, op.1

Alto Sax/ Clarinet

Piano

mp

tr

asax/cl

cresc.

L.H.

tr

sfp

asax/cl

tr

mf

L.H.

33
asax/cl

pf

35
asax/cl

pf

37
asax/cl

pf

40
asax/cl

pf

43

asax/cl

mf *f* *dim.* *pp*

pf

L.H.

cresc. *fp*

R.H.

poco a poco cresc.

46

asax/cl

p

pf

L.H.

rit. molto

49

asax/cl

f *ff* *dim.*

pf

L.H.

f *ff* *dim.*

Lentiss.

51

asax/cl

pp

pf

L.H.

pp

Tempo I, ben ritmato (♩ = 63)

55

asax/cl

mf *cresc.*

pf

mf *cresc.*

rit. ad lib.

59

asax/cl

ff *p*

8

pf

ff *dim.*

L.H.

3

a tempo

62

asax/cl

p *cresc.* *mf*

tr

pf

mp

64

asax/cl

morendo *p* *f*

ridicolo!
un poco growling

pf

morendo *R.H.* *L.H.* *pp* *sfz* *sfz* *mf*

f *no Ped!* *secco*

ped. (1/2)